

Greek terms in anatomical terminology: Historical development and implications for medical and pharmaceutical education

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Abstract

Greek anatomical terminology represents a historically continuous linguistic foundation of modern medical and pharmaceutical sciences. This study examines the development, etymological structure, and educational significance of Greek-derived anatomical terms within standardized anatomical nomenclature. The analysis indicates that many Greek terms preserve semantic transparency, metaphorical imagery, and conceptual precision, whereas their Latinized forms often create challenges related to declension, pronunciation, and interdisciplinary comprehension. Terms such as *trachea*, *aorta*, *arteria*, *thalamus*, *encephalon*, *pharynx*, and *skeleton* demonstrate how anatomical naming combines descriptive, functional, and metaphorical principles. The findings indicate that etymology-based instruction, problem-based learning, visual resources, and curricular integration can improve terminology acquisition in medical and pharmaceutical education. Understanding the historical and linguistic foundations of anatomical terminology strengthens professional communication, terminological accuracy, and interdisciplinary competence in contemporary healthcare.

Keywords

Anatomical nomenclature, etymology, Greek terminology, medical education, pharmaceutical education

Introduction

Anatomical terminology is predominantly derived from Greek and Latin and remains one of the most stable linguistic systems in modern biomedical communication. Greek terms occupy a particularly important position due to the historical origins of European medicine in ancient Greece. Many anatomical designations introduced in the works of Homer, Hippocrates, Herophilus, Erasistratus, and Galen continue to exist in contemporary international nomenclature.

The importance of Greek terminology extends beyond historical continuity. In modern healthcare education,

medical and pharmaceutical students are required to master a complex multilingual vocabulary that forms the basis of anatomy, physiology, pathology, pharmacology, and clinical communication. Anatomical terminology therefore functions not only as a descriptive linguistic system but also as an educational instrument supporting professional literacy and interdisciplinary communication.

Within pharmaceutical education, Greek-derived terminology is equally significant because pharmaceutical nomenclature, pharmacognosy, pharmacology, and clinical pharmacy frequently rely on anatomical and physiological concepts. Future pharmacists must accurately

understand terms related to body systems, organs, tissues, and routes of drug administration to communicate effectively with physicians and patients. Consequently, the study of anatomical terminology has direct implications for both medical and pharmaceutical training.

The present paper examines the historical development and linguistic structure of Greek anatomical terminology, while focusing specifically on its educational significance for contemporary medical and pharmaceutical curricula. The study analyzes the preservation and adaptation of Greek forms in modern nomenclature and discusses pedagogical strategies that facilitate the acquisition of specialized terminology among medical and pharmacy students.

Historical development of Greek anatomical terminology

Early Greek medical tradition

The origins of anatomical terminology can be traced to ancient Greek medicine, where early physicians and philosophers attempted to describe the structure and function of the human body using metaphorical, spatial, and functional linguistic models. The rationalizing tendencies of early Greek medicine contributed to the gradual transformation of bodily vocabulary from ordinary descriptive language into a more systematic medical lexicon (Longrigg 1993). Homeric descriptions of body parts, including terms such as *gaster* and *glossa*, later entered scientific medical language and became integrated into formal anatomical terminology.

Hippocratic medicine played a central role in the formation of early Greek medical vocabulary and in the gradual development of a more systematic language for describing the human body. Although anatomical knowledge in classical Greece was limited by the absence of systematic human dissection, the Hippocratic Corpus demonstrates the growing importance of bodily observation, clinical reasoning, and descriptive terminology in medical thought (Longrigg 1993; Nutton 2013). Terms such as *hepar*, *lobus*, and *peritoneum* illustrate the enduring influence of Greek medical vocabulary on modern anatomical language.

In Alexandria, Herophilus and Erasistratus contributed decisively to the development of anatomical science by introducing a more empirical and observational approach to the study of the human body. Herophilus, in particular, is associated with some of the earliest systematic anatomical investigations in the Western medical tradition, including descriptions of the nervous system and internal organs (von Staden 1989). Together, the Alexandrian anatomists helped establish a more precise anatomical vocabulary grounded in observation, classification, and structural differentiation.

Claudius Galenus (131–216 AD) further consolidated Greek anatomical terminology within Roman medicine. Writing predominantly in Greek, Galen systematized anatomical and physiological knowledge in a form that remained authoritative throughout medieval and Renaissance medicine. His descriptions of cerebral structures,

nerves, and internal organs contributed significantly to the transmission of Greek anatomical vocabulary into later medical traditions (Rocca 2003). Terms such as *thalamus*, *sternum*, and *cremaster* illustrate the lasting influence of Galenic terminology on later anatomical nomenclature.

Standardization of anatomical nomenclature

The modernization and standardization of anatomical terminology became necessary due to the existence of multiple synonyms, regional variations, and eponyms (O’Rahilly 1989; Sakai 2007). The Basel Nomina Anatomica (BNA 1895) represented the first systematic attempt to unify anatomical terminology internationally. Subsequent revisions included the Jena Nomina Anatomica (JNA 1935) and the Paris Nomina Anatomica (PNA 1955). The publication of “Terminologia Anatomica” in 1998 marked a major milestone in contemporary nomenclature (Whitmore 1999). The second edition, published online by the Federative International Programme for Anatomical Terminology (FIPAT) in 2019 and approved by the International Federation of Associations of Anatomists (IFAA) General Assembly in 2020, continues to provide internationally accepted anatomical terminology in Latin and English (FIPAT 2019). Recent commentary has emphasized that this revision represents an evolution rather than a radical break with established usage, while debate continues over the balance between linguistic correctness and terminological stability (Neumann 2023; Waschke 2024).

For modern medical and pharmaceutical education, standardization is essential because students must operate within an internationally recognized professional vocabulary. A unified anatomical terminology supports precise professional communication and reduces ambiguity in interdisciplinary contexts involving physicians, pharmacists, dentists, nurses, and biomedical researchers (Whitmore 1999; FIPAT 2019).

Materials and methods

The present study applies a qualitative historical-linguistic approach to the analysis of Greek-derived anatomical terminology.

Study design

The methodological framework combines historical-philological analysis of primary and secondary sources with an educational interpretation oriented toward contemporary medical and pharmaceutical curricula.

Literature identification

Relevant literature was identified through structured searches of PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar, complemented by targeted examination of standard reference

works on the history of anatomy and anatomical nomenclature. Search terms combined keywords such as “anatomical terminology,” “Greek medical terms,” “etymology,” “Terminologia Anatomica,” “medical education,” and “pharmaceutical education.” Both classical primary sources, in modern critical editions and translations, and peer-reviewed secondary literature were considered, with particular attention to publications addressing terminology instruction in the health professions.

Sources

The analysis draws upon:

- Classical Greek and Latin medical texts, including Hippocratic and Galenic writings;
- Historical studies on ancient medicine and anatomical nomenclature;
- Official anatomical standards, including BNA, JNA, PNA, and the first and second editions of “Terminologia Anatomica”;
- Contemporary literature in medical and pharmaceutical education.

Selection criteria

The study focuses on:

- Anatomical terms of Greek origin preserved in modern nomenclature;
- Terms demonstrating varying degrees of Latinization;
- Examples illustrating metaphorical and semantic mechanisms in anatomical naming;
- Pedagogical challenges associated with terminology instruction in medicine and pharmacy.

Selection of terms

Anatomical terms were selected purposively to illustrate representative linguistic and pedagogical phenomena rather than to provide exhaustive coverage. Inclusion criteria were as follows: (i) demonstrable Greek origin; (ii) continued presence in current standardized nomenclature (“Terminologia Anatomica”, second edition); and (iii) value as an example of a morphological, etymological, or metaphorical mechanism relevant to teaching. Terms exhibiting different degrees of Latinization were deliberately included to demonstrate the range of morphological adaptation.

Analytical framework

The analysis includes: (i) diachronic tracing of terminology from antiquity to contemporary codification; (ii) morphological comparison between preserved Greek forms and Latinized forms; (iii) etymological

and semantic interpretation of selected terms; and (iv) educational analysis related to terminology acquisition among medical and pharmacy students.

Limitations

As a qualitative review, the study does not provide quantitative frequency data on Greek-derived terms within current standards, nor does it report primary empirical measurements of learning outcomes; these are identified as directions for future research.

Results

Morphological adaptation and latinization

Greek anatomical terms demonstrate different levels of morphological preservation and adaptation within Latin anatomical nomenclature. This process reflects the broader incorporation of Greek medical vocabulary into Latin technical language, where borrowed terms could either preserve elements of their original Greek morphology or be reshaped according to Latin grammatical patterns (Langslow 2000).

First declension

Certain Greek terms preserve their original morphology, while others appear in Latinized forms. For example:

- *Rhaphē* (“seam”) retains Greek structure;
- *Pleura* and *amygdala* are fully assimilated into Latin declensional patterns.

Second declension

Neuter nouns ending in *-on* coexist with Latinized forms ending in *-um*:

- *Acromion*, *olecranon*;
- *Sternum* derived from Greek *sternon*.

Masculine forms frequently adopt the Latin ending *-us*, as in *lobus* from Greek *lobos*.

Distribution across anatomical systems

Greek-derived terminology remains especially prominent in:

- The circulatory and respiratory systems (*aorta*, *trachea*, *pleura*);
- Neuroanatomy (*thalamus*, *encephalon*, *ganglion*, *neuron*);
- Skeletal anatomy (*acromion*, *ischium*, *phalanx*);
- Digestive anatomy (*colon*, *pylorus*, *peritoneum*);
- Histological structures (*myocardium*, *endocardium*, *epimysium*).

Etymological and semantic models

Many anatomical terms preserve metaphorical and descriptive meanings that support conceptual understanding.

- *Trachea* derives from the Greek expression meaning “rough artery,” referring to the cartilaginous texture of the windpipe;
- *Arteria* originally signified an “air-holder,” reflecting ancient physiological theories;
- *Thalamus* means “inner chamber,” metaphorically describing the central cerebral structure;
- *Phalanx* refers to a military formation, illustrating the ordered arrangement of finger and toe bones;
- *Pylorus* means “gatekeeper,” describing the regulatory function between the stomach and duodenum.

These examples demonstrate that Greek anatomical terminology combines descriptive morphology, spatial orientation, and metaphorical imagery.

Discussion

Educational challenges in medical and pharmaceutical training

The acquisition of anatomical terminology remains one of the major challenges in the early stages of medical and pharmaceutical education. Students are required to memorize large numbers of unfamiliar lexical units while simultaneously understanding their clinical and functional significance. Empirical research suggests that familiarity with Latin and Greek anatomical terms may be related to course performance, although this relationship appears to be weak and cannot replace contextual, functional, and concept-based learning (Pam-push and Petto 2011).

- Greek-derived terms create additional complexity because students must learn the following:
- Greek roots and prefixes;
- Latin grammatical endings and declensions;
- Semantic relationships between anatomical structures;
- Clinically relevant applications of terminology.

For medical students, anatomical terminology forms the basis of clinical reasoning, diagnostic interpretation, surgery, radiology, and pathology. Incorrect understanding of terminology may negatively affect professional communication and patient safety.

For pharmacy students, anatomical terminology is essential in pharmacology, pharmacotherapy, toxicology, pharmaceutical care, and patient counseling. Pharmacists must accurately interpret anatomical references in prescriptions, adverse-effect descriptions, contraindications, and mechanisms of drug action. Therefore, insufficient terminological competence may limit interdisciplinary communication between pharmacists and physicians.

The educational challenge is intensified in multilingual academic environments where students possess different linguistic backgrounds. Learners whose native languages lack inflectional grammatical systems often encounter greater difficulty with Latin and Greek declensions.

Greek terminology in pharmaceutical education

Although anatomical nomenclature is most often discussed in relation to medical training, Greek-derived terminology is equally foundational to pharmaceutical education, where it extends well beyond anatomy into the core vocabulary of the discipline itself. The very name of the field derives from the Greek *pharmakon*, denoting remedy, drug, and poison, and this root generates a dense network of professional terms, including *pharmacology*, *pharmacognosy*, *pharmacokinetics*, *pharmacodynamics*, and *pharmacopeia*. Each of these compounds couples *pharmakon* with another Greek element—*gnosis* (knowledge), *kinesis* (movement), *dynamis* (power), and *poiein* (to make)—so that the structure of the lexicon itself encodes the conceptual structure of the discipline.

Greek roots are similarly embedded in the terminology of drug action and administration. Terms such as *narcotic* (*narkē*, numbness), *analgesic* (*algos*, pain), *antidote* (*antidotos*, given against), *-lysis* and *-lytic* (*lysis*, loosening, as in *thrombolytic*), and *emesis / antiemetic* (*emein*, to vomit) recur throughout pharmacology and pharmacotherapy. Routes of drug administration are described with the same classical apparatus: *enteral* and *parenteral* administration derive from *enteron* (intestine), while terms for organ systems and tissues—themselves largely Greek in origin—are indispensable for describing drug targets, mechanisms of action, contraindications, and adverse effects.

For pharmacy students, command of this vocabulary is therefore not ancillary but central to the core concepts of pharmacology, which recent research has sought to define explicitly as the conceptual scaffolding of the discipline (White et al. 2021). Accurate interpretation of anatomical and physiological references is essential when pharmacists review prescriptions, counsel patients, and communicate with physicians about mechanisms of drug action and organ-specific effects. Insufficient terminological competence may consequently constrain interprofessional communication and, ultimately, the quality of pharmaceutical care. Etymology-based and concept-oriented instruction, as increasingly advocated in medical terminology teaching (Cortés et al. 2024), is therefore equally relevant to the preparation of future pharmacists.

Implications for medical and pharmaceutical education

Modern educational research demonstrates that rote memorization alone is insufficient for effective terminology acquisition. Instead, contemporary teaching approaches emphasize contextualized and interdisciplinary learning.

Etymology-based instruction

Etymological explanation may facilitate long-term retention by associating terminology with meaningful conceptual images. Understanding that *pylorus* means “gatekeeper” or that *phalanx* refers to a military formation enables students to create semantic associations between linguistic form, anatomical structure, and function. However, empirical findings suggest that familiarity with Greek and Latin anatomical terms should be regarded as a supportive component of terminology learning rather than as a sufficient condition for successful course performance (Pampush and Petto 2011).

Problem-based learning

Problem-based learning integrates terminology into realistic clinical and pharmaceutical scenarios. By situating anatomical vocabulary within diagnostic cases, pharmacotherapeutic contexts, and interdisciplinary discussions, this approach supports practical comprehension, active knowledge construction, and the application of terminology in professionally relevant contexts (Dolmans et al. 2005).

Visual and digital learning resources

Visual learning strategies—including anatomical atlases, schematic diagrams, 3D anatomical platforms, and digital glossaries—support the spatial understanding of anatomical terminology. Digital educational resources aligned with the second edition of “Terminologia Anatomica” may improve accessibility and consistency in terminology instruction.

Interdisciplinary integration

Anatomical terminology should not be isolated within introductory language courses. Instead, it should be integrated across anatomy, physiology, pathology, pharmacology, and clinical disciplines. Core anatomy syllabi in medical education emphasize structured learning outcomes and curricular integration, supporting the view that terminology should function as part of a broader anatomical and clinical competence rather than as a separate memorization task (Smith et al. 2016).

Relevance for professional communication

The internationalization of healthcare increasingly requires physicians and pharmacists to communicate across linguistic and cultural boundaries. Greek-derived

anatomical terminology, integrated into standardized international nomenclature, functions as a shared professional vocabulary that facilitates scientific exchange, clinical collaboration, and pharmaceutical communication worldwide (Whitmore 1999; FIPAT 2019).

Consequently, terminology education contributes not only to academic performance but also to professional competence, interdisciplinary communication, and patient-centered healthcare.

Conclusion

Greek anatomical terminology represents a historically continuous and linguistically sophisticated system that remains central to modern medicine and pharmacy. The preservation of Greek semantic structures within contemporary nomenclature demonstrates the enduring scientific influence of ancient medical language.

At the same time, Greek-derived terminology creates important pedagogical challenges due to its morphological complexity, semantic density, and interdisciplinary nature. Effective terminology instruction therefore requires educational approaches that combine historical explanation, clinical application, etymology-based learning, problem-based instruction, and curricular integration (Dolmans et al. 2005; Pampush and Petto 2011; Smith et al. 2016).

For medical students, mastery of anatomical terminology supports accurate clinical communication and diagnostic reasoning. For pharmacy students, terminological competence is equally important for understanding pharmacological mechanisms, pharmaceutical care, and interdisciplinary collaboration.

The integration of etymology-based learning, problem-based instruction, and modern digital educational resources may transform terminology education from passive memorization into meaningful conceptual understanding. Such an interdisciplinary approach strengthens linguistic precision, professional communication, and international academic integration in contemporary healthcare education.

Future research should focus on:

- Quantitative analyses of Greek terminology in contemporary anatomical standards;
- Comparative studies between medical and pharmaceutical curricula;
- Development of bilingual and multilingual digital terminology platforms;
- Evaluation of educational strategies that improve long-term terminology retention.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
